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RESEARCH

EXPLORING THE ADOPTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE INDIAN HEALTHCARE SYSTEM: THE CASE OF CANCER TREATMENT

Deepshikha Chhaperia, Dr. Kamini Khanna*

Abstract

On the Indian subcontinent, where a billion hearts beat, cancer casts a long shadow. In this crucible of healthcare innovation, the researchers shift their focus to India, a land as diverse as its challenges. This research delves deep into the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) to transform cancer care within India's unique ecosystem. Journeying to Kharghar, Maharashtra, a microcosm of the nation's hopes and realities, the researchers assess the community's attitude towards embracing AI-driven solutions. But amidst the enthusiasm lies a sobering truth: the specter of high cancer care costs looms large across India's healthcare landscape. This research serves as a call to action, urging targeted government interventions tailored to the Indian context. Envisioning a future where AI-powered cancer care is democratized, hope replaces despair for millions battling this formidable foe

Keywords : Artificial intelligence (AI), Healthcare, India, Cancer care, Cost

Introduction

“Health is wealth,” as the age-old adage goes, yet for many in today’s India, achieving true health remains a distant dream, especially in places like Kharghar, and Maharashtra, where access to quality healthcare is a constant struggle. But amidst these challenges, there’s a glimmer of hope shining through - Artificial Intelligence (AI). It’s where innovation meets possibility, holding the promise to transform healthcare for millions. In the face of critical issues like affordability and accessibility, AI stands as a beacon of hope, offering revolutionary solutions.

In India, healthcare mirrors the struggles of many developing nations, burdened by diseases like cancer and limited resources. While AI presents innovative solutions, the reality is that its benefits are often out of reach for a significant portion of the population. This research delves into the aspirations and hurdles faced by India and similar nations in leveraging AI in healthcare. It emphasizes the urgent need for government

intervention to make these transformative technologies accessible and affordable, ultimately aiming to reduce mortality rates and provide hope to millions. In semi-urban and rural areas of India, healthcare access is marred by vast disparities, with diseases like cancer, diabetes, and cardiovascular ailments posing significant challenges. Early detection is crucial, yet the shortage of healthcare professionals and stretched-thin infrastructure hinder effective diagnosis and treatment.

The potential of AI in Indian healthcare is vast. With its ability to analyze vast amounts of healthcare data, AI offers solutions ranging from early disease detection to precision medicine and telemedicine. AI-powered systems can analyze medical images like X-rays and CT scans, facilitating accurate diagnoses, particularly in regions with a scarcity of specialists. Moreover, predictive analytics by AI can identify individuals at risk of diseases, enabling preventive care—a proactive approach crucial in a country where healthcare resources are limited.

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However, the reality of the cost barrier cannot be ignored. AI technologies in healthcare come with a hefty price tag, making them inaccessible to many in developing nations like India, where a significant population lives below the poverty line. Additionally, low digital literacy poses a significant challenge in the widespread adoption of AI-driven healthcare solutions, particularly in rural areas. Limited exposure to technology and health information literacy further compounds the issue, highlighting the need for comprehensive government intervention.

Governments in developing countries must recognize AI in healthcare as a necessity, not a luxury, and invest in research, development, and partnerships with AI technology providers to ensure affordability and accessibility. Public-private partnerships hold promise in leveraging resources and expertise to deploy AI healthcare solutions effectively, tailored to the specific needs of the population.

The challenges and opportunities presented by AI in healthcare resonate across many Asian countries. Awareness campaigns and government initiatives are crucial to addressing barriers to healthcare access, ultimately offering hope for improved healthcare outcomes across the region. AI's role in the health sector is pivotal, promising transformative solutions to address longstanding healthcare disparities and enhance the quality of life for millions across Asia.

Literature Review:

In the landscape of healthcare across India, where cancer incidence is on the rise, there's a growing need for innovative solutions to address the healthcare challenges. One such solution is the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the field of medicine, offering a glimmer of hope for improved diagnosis and patient care.

Table 1.1 Summary of Literature Review

Title	Year	Author	Findings
Dermatologist-level classification of skin cancer with deep neural networks	2017	Esteva et al.	Esteva et al. demonstrated the efficacy of deep learning algorithms in classifying skin lesions with a level of accuracy comparable to board-certified dermatologists. This breakthrough study showcased the potential of AI in dermatology, particularly in improving early cancer detection and reducing the need for invasive procedures such as biopsies.
A survey on deep learning in medical image analysis	2017	Litjens et al.	Litjens et al. conducted a comprehensive survey highlighting the transformative impact of AI, particularly deep learning, in medical image analysis. By augmenting diagnostic accuracy, AI-powered algorithms have the potential to revolutionize cancer diagnosis, transcending geographical boundaries and healthcare settings.
Automated breast cancer diagnosis using deep learning and data fusion	Not specified	Wang et al.	Wang et al. introduced an innovative approach combining Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) to enhance diagnostic accuracy in breast cancer diagnosis. By integrating image analysis with demographic data, this study exemplifies how AI-driven technologies can streamline diagnostic processes and improve patient outcomes.

Title	Year	Author	Findings
Automated diagnosis and classification of liver cancer using deep learning and radionics	Not specified	Hwang	Hwang's study focused on the integration of radionics data with deep learning models to enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of liver cancer diagnosis. This approach has significant implications for resource-constrained regions like India, where timely and accurate cancer detection is crucial for improving patient outcomes.
Predicting cancer outcomes with multi-modal data fusion: A deep learning approach.	Not specified	Chen et al.	Chen et al. proposed a multi-modal data fusion approach leveraging deep learning techniques to predict cancer outcomes. By integrating diverse data sources such as genomics, imaging, and clinical data, this study exemplifies the potential of AI in personalized cancer treatment, facilitating more targeted and effective interventions.
Enhancing cancer immunotherapy response prediction with deep learning.	Not specified	Lee et al.	Lee et al. investigated the use of deep learning algorithms to predict patient responses to cancer immunotherapy. By analyzing complex biomolecular data, including tumor mutational burden and immune cell profiles, this study highlights the role of AI in optimizing treatment strategies and improving patient outcomes in the era of precision medicine.

While AI holds immense potential to optimize cancer treatment and reduce costs, affordability remains a significant hurdle to widespread adoption across Asian countries. The promise of AI-driven cancer care is hampered by the formidable price tags associated with these technologies. Consequently, ensuring universal access to AI-driven healthcare remains an ongoing challenge in many parts of the region.

Objective:

This research paper seeks to address a critical issue at the intersection of healthcare and technology: the urgent necessity of democratizing access to Artificial Intelligence (AI) in healthcare, particularly in developing nations like India. Our primary objective is to delve into the multifaceted challenges and promising opportunities associated with AI adoption in healthcare. We aim to underscore how AI can be a transformative force in narrowing healthcare disparities, reducing mortality rates,

and vastly enhancing healthcare accessibility in resource-constrained regions. By examining the Indian context as a case study, this research endeavors to advocate for visionary government policies, foster collaborative public-private partnerships and catalyze innovative strategies to render AI-powered healthcare solutions affordable, available, and life-saving for the masses.

Research methodology:

The study is exploratory and centered on a survey-based approach. It seeks to comprehensively investigate the perception and potential for adopting artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare, with a specific focus on developing and underdeveloped regions, notably within Navi Mumbai's Kharghar area, India. To ensure diverse perspectives, a random sampling approach was employed. In this endeavor, the researcher engaged with 25 cancer patients out of 100 (on the basis of random sampling technique) who had experienced AI-based healthcare technologies.

Data was collected through a structured questionnaire employing a five-point Likert scale for responses, where 1 indicates strong agreement and 5 indicates strong disagreement. Demographic variables, including age, gender, education, profession, and geographic location, were incorporated into the data collection process. Data analysis was facilitated using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), and the reliability of the survey instrument was evaluated through Cronbach's Alpha. Additionally, multiple regression analysis was employed to delve into the implications of AI adoption within the healthcare sector, specifically assessing the receptiveness of patients and healthcare stakeholders to the utilization of AI-based technologies, including robotic surgery, in the context of cancer treatment. The methodology employed in this study is more than a mere academic exercise. It serves as a pivotal cornerstone for shaping informed policy decisions and strategic initiatives. Ultimately, it aims to pave the way for more accessible and affordable AI adoption within the healthcare domain. By doing so, it seeks to address the overarching goal of improving healthcare outcomes and substantially reducing mortality rates, especially in resource-constrained regions where the need for transformative healthcare solutions is most pressing and acute.

Hypothesis:

H0: Artificial intelligence in healthcare does not significantly impact patients' feelings of fear.

H1: Artificial intelligence in healthcare significantly affects patients' feelings of fear, leading to improved trust and confidence in medical interventions.

Questionnaire structure:

The questionnaire (Table 1.2) is divided into two sections: the first focuses on the demographics of cancer patients, and the second asks about their

opinions about the use of artificial intelligence in the healthcare sector.

Table 1.2

Section	Category	
Section One	General	Demographic information like name of the person, age, education
Section Two	Opinions about the use of artificial intelligence in the healthcare sector	Focuses on respondents' views regarding the implementation of AI in healthcare and their concerns or fears related to it.

Interface:

In Table 1.2: Section one collects demographic data, while section two gauges respondents' willingness to see AI used in healthcare, their ability to bear the costs of robotic surgery, and their anxiety or fear regarding AI.

Results and Discussion:

Reliability Measure:

Reliability analysis via Cronbach's coefficient alpha was conducted to assess the consistency of questionnaire statements. The alpha is a figure that ranges between 0 and 1. According to Cohen (2007), Cronbach's alpha value at 0.6 is marginally reliable while 0.91 or above is highly reliable. He also suggested that Cronbach's alpha value which is over 0.89 shows good estimates of internal consistency reliability. Cronbach's alpha value which is over 0.89 shows good estimates of internal consistency reliability. Cronbach's alpha value was calculated as follows:

$$\frac{N^2 \times M(\text{COV})}{\text{SUM}(\text{VAR}/\text{COV})}$$

Where N^2 = is the square of the number of items in the scale $m(COV)$ = is the mean interterm covariance

Sum (VAR/COV) = equals the sum of all the elements in the variance/ covariance matrix Reliability for the questionnaire was calculated through SPSS. The statistics (Table 1.3) came out as:

Table 1.3 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.896	.982	6

It is considered that the reliability value should be more than 0.7, and it can be seen that in statistics, the reliability value was (.896) higher than the standard value, so all items in the questionnaire are reliable for study. Hence no changes were made to the questionnaire and all the items were retained for further analysis.

Taken from: (Impact of Brand Equity on Purchase Intension of Home Appliances, 2017)

Data Analysis:

Due to the limited sample size and data source constraints, the study acknowledges its limitations in generalizing results. The demographic variables considered included gender and age.

Table 1.4 Gender Profile of the Respondent

Gender	Percent
Male	46%
Female	54%
Total	100%

From Table 1.4, we know that out of the total respondents, 50% belonged to the 20-35 years category, followed by 46% belonging to the

35-45 years category, with only 4% belonging to the 45 years and above category.

Table 1.5 Age of the Respondent

Age	Percent	Cumulative percentage
25-35	50%	50%
35-45	46%	96%
45 and above	4%	100%
Total	100%	

Table 1.6 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
AI-based device	4.04	1.654	25
AI implementation	2.08	.929	25
Fear of AI in medical treatment	2.38	1.096	25
Willingness for robotic surgery	2.13	1.035	25
Financial capacity	2.04	.908	25
Nervousness about AI in medical treatment	.46	.509	25

From this table, it's apparent that the standard deviation is extremely low, almost approaching zero. This indicates that the data points are clustered closely around the mean.

Table 1.7 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.982 ^a	.865	.802	.612

a. Predictors: (Constant), Nervousness about AI in medical treatment, the willingness for robotic surgery, financial capacity, Fear of AI in medical treatment, AI implementation

Table 1.8 ANOVA Analysis

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	16.012	6	2.668	2.779	.002 ^b
	Residual	18.388	19	0.967		
	Total	34.400	25			

a. Dependent Variable: AI-based device

b. Predictors: (Constant), Nervousness about AI in medical treatment, the willingness for robotic surgery, financial capacity, Fear of AI in medical treatment, AI implementation

Table 1.9 Coefficients of the Variables

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.649	2.239		1.630	.020
AI implementation	.506	.520	.684	.974	.043
Fear of AI in medical treatment	-.129	.433	-.385	-.298	.053
Willingness for robotic surgery	.110	.418	.069	.263	.796
Financial capacity	.116	.478	.064	.243	.811
Nervousness about AI in medical treatment	-.787	.811	-.442	-.970	.034

a. Dependent Variable: AI-based device

According to the study (Table 1.9), there exists a negative correlation between nervousness (-.787) and fear (-.129) when receiving medical treatment. This suggests that as the use of artificial intelligence (AI) and robotic surgery continues to grow, fear and anxiety are likely to decrease.

The value of R² equals 0.865, indicating that 86.5 percent of the variations in AI-based device usage can be explained by factors like the implementation of AI, willingness to accept robotic surgery, fear or nervousness regarding AI in medical treatment, and the ability to bear the associated expenditure. The value of R² is

statistically significant as indicated by the p-value (0.002) in the ANOVA Table. The estimated regression equation as obtained in the table may be written as:

$$Y = 3.649 + 0.506X_1 + 0.110X_2 - 0.129X_3 - 0.787X_4 + 0.116X_5$$

P value = (.020) (.043) (.796) (.053) (.034) (.811)
Beta coefficient = (.684) (.069) (-.385) (-.442) (.069)

X₁ = AI implementation

X₂ = willingness for robotic surgery

X₃ = fear of AI in medical treatment

X₄ = nervousness about AI in medical treatment

X₅ = financial capacity

In selecting the variables for our regression equation, researchers aimed to capture key dimensions related to patients' perceptions and attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare. The variables were chosen based on their relevance to understanding the impact of AI on patient fear and nervousness in medical treatment.

Firstly, we included variables related to fear and nervousness about AI in medical treatment (-.129 and -.787) to examine their negative associations with AI-based device usage. These variables are crucial as they reflect the psychological and emotional responses of patients toward the adoption of AI technology in healthcare settings. Understanding the factors contributing to patient apprehension is essential for devising strategies to address and alleviate these concerns, thereby facilitating the acceptance and adoption of AI-driven healthcare solutions.

On the other hand, variables related to AI implementation, willingness to accept robotic surgery, and expenditure (.506, .110, and .116) were included to explore their positive associations with AI-based device usage. These variables are indicative of patients' receptiveness towards embracing AI technologies in healthcare, their readiness to undergo innovative procedures such as robotic surgery, and their financial capacity to bear the costs associated with AI-driven healthcare interventions. By examining these variables, we aim to elucidate the factors that promote the adoption and utilization of AI-based healthcare solutions among patients.

The beta coefficient of 0.684 for the implementation of AI underscores its relative importance in influencing patients' attitudes and behaviors toward AI-based healthcare solutions. This coefficient indicates the magnitude of the impact of AI implementation on patient perceptions, highlighting the significant role of AI technologies in shaping the future of healthcare delivery.

Furthermore, it's crucial to acknowledge the substantial financial implications associated with AI adoption in healthcare, particularly in countries like India with diverse economic backgrounds. The cost of AI implementation and robotic surgeries can be prohibitive, potentially limiting access for those with limited financial means. Beyond financial considerations, our research recognizes several other bottlenecks, including disparities in literacy levels and deeply entrenched sociocultural beliefs prevalent in rural areas. These factors contribute to the complexity of AI adoption in healthcare, necessitating nuanced strategies and awareness campaigns to address them effectively.

By including these variables in our regression equation and providing a comprehensive explanation of their selection, the study aims to offer insights into the multifaceted nature of AI adoption in healthcare and its implications for patient perceptions and behaviors.

Discussion:

Our research uncovers a significant enthusiasm among people for incorporating AI-based technology into healthcare. Nevertheless, we must grapple with the financial hurdles linked to AI adoption, notably in regions like India. The data highlights the urgency of government intervention to ensure that AI-driven healthcare solutions reach all sections of society. Such steps could involve subsidies, financial backing for research and development, and the creation of cost-effective healthcare facilities equipped with AI.

In the realm of AI in healthcare, it's worth noting that the global landscape is showing encouraging signs. The numbers we've presented in this section indicate a remarkable surge in the AI healthcare market, with substantial investments and growing confidence among healthcare professionals in AI technologies. Moreover, AI holds the potential to generate substantial cost savings for the

healthcare sector, supported by estimates that suggest AI applications could dramatically reduce annual healthcare expenditures.

Furthermore, we're witnessing a rising trend in implementing AI for medical diagnosis, offering the prospect of reduced treatment costs and enhanced health outcomes. For example, research from Harvard's School of Public Health indicates that AI-driven diagnoses could lead to cost reductions of up to 50% while concurrently improving health outcomes by 40%. Additionally, AI technologies are being explored to enhance breast cancer risk prediction, offering promising avenues for improved healthcare services.

On the global stage, we're observing rapid AI adoption in healthcare, with significant investments and advancements in various countries. For instance, China's government has set ambitious goals to become a frontrunner in AI innovation by 2030, with a particular focus on medical imaging. In South Korea, AI in the healthcare market is anticipated to experience substantial growth, driven by the utilization of big data and AI in medical device software.

Moreover, the global AI in healthcare market is on a trajectory towards substantial valuations in the forthcoming years. The data indicates substantial growth, with projections indicating a reach of USD 45.2 billion by 2026, reflecting a compound annual growth rate of 44.9% (Mehta, March 2023). These trends signify AI's potential to reshape global healthcare delivery and outcomes.

In conclusion, while the adoption of AI in healthcare offers immense potential, especially in addressing critical challenges such as low doctor-patient ratios, uneven expertise distribution, and affordability, it's imperative to acknowledge the central role of government intervention in guaranteeing accessibility and fairness. The financial challenges linked to AI adoption necessitate a collective effort to bridge the divide and fully leverage AI's potential to enhance healthcare outcomes.

Variables were chosen based on their relevance to the study's focus on AI's impact on patient fear in healthcare. Financial capacity was included due to its significant role in healthcare accessibility. However, the study acknowledges other potential influencing factors, such as literacy levels and sociocultural beliefs, which could be explored in future research to provide a comprehensive understanding of AI adoption in healthcare.

Recommendation:

Based on the study findings, several recommendations are proposed to effectively harness the potential of AI in healthcare:

1. Develop AI-driven educational platforms tailored to patients' needs: To alleviate fears and misconceptions surrounding AI in healthcare, it is imperative to develop educational platforms that cater to the specific needs of patients and caregivers. These platforms should provide clear and accessible information about the role of AI in diagnosis, treatment, and patient care, empowering individuals to make informed decisions about their health. Collaborations with healthcare professionals, patient advocacy groups, and technology experts are essential to ensure the accuracy and relevance of educational content.
2. Allocate resources for the implementation of AI technologies in healthcare facilities: To ensure widespread adoption and integration of AI technologies in healthcare, it is essential to allocate sufficient resources for their implementation, particularly in underserved areas like Kharghar. This includes funding for the procurement of AI-enabled medical devices, infrastructure upgrades to support AI-driven systems, and training programs for healthcare professionals to effectively utilize these technologies. Additionally, government initiatives and public-private partnerships can play a crucial role in facilitating the deployment of AI solutions in healthcare facilities across different regions.

3. Foster collaborations between healthcare providers, technology companies, and policy-makers: Ethical and equitable deployment of AI in healthcare requires close collaboration between various stakeholders, including healthcare providers, technology companies, and policymakers. Interdisciplinary collaborations can help ensure that AI-driven solutions are designed and implemented in a manner that prioritizes patient safety, privacy, and equity. Furthermore, policymakers play a critical role in shaping regulatory frameworks and standards for the use of AI in healthcare, and their involvement is essential to addressing legal and ethical considerations associated with AI adoption. By fostering open dialogue and collaboration among these stakeholders, we can create a conducive environment for the responsible and effective integration of AI into the healthcare ecosystem.

Conclusion:

The potential of AI in healthcare is not just a distant dream but a tangible solution for

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countries like India, struggling with healthcare access. However, to realize this potential, governments must play a pivotal role in making AI technologies affordable and accessible to all. The cost barrier cannot be allowed to stand in the way of saving lives.

In India, the case of Kharghar serves as a microcosm of the broader challenges faced by developing and underdeveloped nations. The urgency lies in recognizing that AI in healthcare is not a luxury but a lifeline. It is the responsibility of governments to pave the way for innovation, foster partnerships, and create policies that ensure AI's reach to the masses.

The time has come for developing nations to unlock the transformative power of AI in healthcare and, in doing so, offer hope, accessibility, and a chance at a healthier life to millions who deserve nothing less. The investment is not just in technology; it's an investment in humanity's well-being.

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Core values

1. Passion:

The soul of Welingkar blossoms in our heart, mind and body.

2. Breakthrough Thinking:

We foster academic rigour in an environment conducive to innovation.

3. Result oriented, Process driven Work Ethic:

We adopt dynamic quality processes to ensure accountability and exceptional performances.

4. We Link and Care:

We support and collaborate with all our stakeholders through mutual trust and respect.

Quality policY

We are committed to give our students Quality Management Education in tune with the changing needs of business and industry.

We shall endeavor to do this by:

- Providing the best learning resources.
- Making the environment conducive for students to develop their creativity, Leadership skills and ability to learn continuously.

We shall follow a data oriented factual approach to Quality Management leading to continual improvement of our processes culminating in total customer satisfaction.

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